

EDITORIAL

The Work Continues

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This year, anthropology in Kosova has achieved significant milestones. In October 2024, the University of Prishtina established the Institute of Anthropology (IAUP), which will operate aside the Department of Anthropology, and within the Faculty of Philosophy. This institute aims to advance anthropological research through collaborations with local, regional, and international partners. Additionally, in September 2024, the Department of Anthropology hosted the INASEA conference (International Association for Southeast European Anthropology), where over 100 researchers from various countries presented their work on migration under the theme “*In, Out, and In-Between: Transnational and Internal Migration in Southeast Europe.*”

This year saw the culmination of significant efforts with the opening of the *Krusha e Madhe Massacre Museum* on March 26, 2024, coinciding with the 25th anniversary of the massacre in village of Krusha e Madhe, where 241 Albanians (among them 14 Ashkali) were massacred and forcibly disappeared. The museum stands as a solemn tribute to the lives lost during the massacre and serves as a vital space for preserving the memory of this dark chapter of Kosova’s history. Its creation was the result of four years of tireless collaboration between anthropologists (professors and students), and various local and international partners.

The word “discovery” is most relevant and appropriate when used by archaeologists. However, while discovery usually refers to a singular event, archaeological research is a long and continuous process, more akin to a journey. Kosovan archaeologists are continuing their journey, unveiling new discoveries like mosaics in the Paleochristian church, alongside the famous dedication inscription of Emperor Justinian discovered last year in the archaeological park of Ulpiana. It is important to note that international collaboration has significantly enriched our archaeological journey in Kosova. In recent years, partnerships with the Ecole Normale Supérieure in France, the University of Michigan in the USA, as well as colleagues from Albania, Germany, Italy, and North Macedonia, have propelled archaeological research forward.

In this second volume of *Kosova Anthropologica*, four peer-reviewed articles were selected. These contributions highlight diverse areas such as chemical soil analyses in Ulpiana to interpret historical activities, early carpological studies uncovering agricultural practices in Roman Dardania, early Celtic influences in Northern Italy and the High Adriatic, and the role of return migration in Kosova's rural development.

The first study, led by Arthur Laenger and his team, examines the use of chemical soil analysis in Ulpiana to identify past archaeological activities. Employing EDXRF, a cost-effective technique compared to ICP-MS, the research uncovered evidence of lime preparation pits and a bronze recycling workshop. High concentrations of calcium and strontium in the lime pit suggest construction material presence, while metals like copper, tin, and lead indicate metallurgical activities. A notable element, bromine, possibly linked to prestigious textile dyes used by Roman elites, was also identified. This study underscores the potential of chemical analysis in interpreting archaeological structures and advocates for expanding this methodology to sites like Justiniana Secunda.

Florian Jedrusiak presents a carpological study focusing on early agricultural practices in Ulpiana, providing insights into plant economy and dietary habits between the 1st and 6th centuries AD. By analyzing carbonized plant remains, the study identified locally grown crops like wheat, barley, millet, and legumes, alongside wild fruits such as grapes, walnuts, and elderberries. The absence of imported foods suggests a self-sustaining agricultural system. A distinctive finding was the persistent use of bitter vetch, a unique feature of the Balkans during Roman times. This research establishes a foundation for further studies on agricultural practices in ancient Dardania.

Linda Papi's research delves into the early presence of Celtic communities in Northern Italy and the High Adriatic before the 4th-century BC migrations. The study explores archaeological evidence, including fibulae, weapons, and metallic objects, showcasing interactions between local and Celtic cultures as early as the 7th century BC. Instead of focusing solely on mass migrations, it examines cultural exchanges, individual mobility, and the adoption of Celtic elements by local communities. These findings, such as the integration of Celtic-styled objects as status symbols and trade items, shed light on the cultural dynamics of the Iron Age within a European context.

Finally, Lumnije Kadriu investigates the impact of return migration on rural development in Kosova. Focusing on three cases of migrants returning from Germany, Switzerland, and Slovakia, the study highlights how individuals with limited professional skills established successful businesses in agriculture, organic production, and wine-making. Leveraging financial and social capital gained abroad, these returnees not only improved their social status but also contributed to local development and job creation. The study emphasizes the role of transnational and familial networks in facilitating successful reintegration and entrepreneurship in rural Kosova.

Overall, the papers in this volume underscore the diverse and innovative approaches in anthropology and archaeology, demonstrating the significant steps Kosova is making in advancing anthropological knowledge of the past and the present.